

HIGH-VELOCITY IMPACT BEHAVIOUR OF ADDITIVELY MANUFACTURED CELLULAR CORE BACKED KEVLAR

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ABSTRACT

This work investigates the effect of several parameters of a cellular core, protected by a Kevlar plate, under ballistic impact. Three core geometries, two sizes, and four relative densities are explored and their effects quantified. Overall, auxetic geometries (re-entrant and double arrowhead) result in a significant reduction in transmitted force at the cost of increasing the maximum displacement compared to a non-auxetic hexagonal structure. The cell size has no effect on the maximum displacement for any of the geometries or the transmitted force for the auxetics. A smaller cell size does, nonetheless, increase the peak transmitted force for the hexagonal structure. Increasing the relative density of the structures increases the transmitted force whilst decreasing the maximum displacement across all unit cells considered. This work provides a basis for the parameter selection when using cellular structures in an impact mitigation setting.

1 INTRODUCTION

Head injuries are the primary cause of death on the battlefield [1]. The use of combat helmets, typically comprised of a Kevlar (aramid fibre) shell and foam padding, can still result in traumatic brain injury (TBI) to the wearer after a ballistic impact [2]. Kevlar has a high toughness making it suitable for use in protection against challenging scenarios such as stabbings and ballistic impacts.

Using cellular structures is an option to improve energy absorption whilst maintaining a lightweight and breathable construction. Auxetic (negative Poisson's ratio) structures are known to possess improved impact properties compared to their non-auxetic counterparts. Such structures, whilst difficult to manufacture with traditional techniques, can be realised with additive manufacturing (AM) where fused filament fabrication (FFF) allows for the incorporation of fibres within a polymer matrix allowing for the high strength-to-weight ratio of composites to be utilised.

This study explores the benefit of incorporating an additively manufactured cellular core behind a Kevlar face sheet to improve protection against high-velocity ballistic impacts. Three unit cells (hexagonal, re-entrant and double arrowhead), four relative densities (20%, 30%, 40% and 50%) and two unit cell sizes were investigated. The effects of these parameters on the mechanical response, namely the maximum displacement and peak force transmitted, are discussed in this paper.

2 FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

2.1 Model overview

The set-up, shown in Figure 1, consists of a 130 mm square of 10 mm thick Kevlar backed with a 30 mm thick 3D-printed structure. The assembly is held in position by rigid clamps that extend 15 mm from the edge of the specimen, leaving the central 100 × 100 mm free. A 9 mm full metal jacket (FMJ) bullet, modelled as a lead core with brass outer shell [3], impacts the structure at 358 m/s, in

accordance with NIJ-STD-0106.01 standard. Abaqus 2020 [4] was used to build a finite element (FE) model, shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Schematic of set-up, showing 9 mm FMJ bullet impacting a Kevlar plate supported by a cellular structure.

Figure 2: FE model of setup.

2.1 Face sheet

To accurately model the ballistic behaviour of the Kevlar face sheet a user material (VUMAT) is used and calibrated against experimental data taken from the literature [5]. This subroutine implements the Hashin-Fabric criteria [6] along with progressive damage evolution to model the intralaminar behaviour. This consists of six failure modes, Table 1, allowing the bi-directional strength of the woven material to be considered. Material properties are taken from Tan et al [7], Tables 2 & 3.

Failure Mode	Failure Initiation Criteria
Fibre 1 tension ($\sigma_1 > 0$)	$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{X_{1T}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 \geq 1$
Fibre 1 compression ($\sigma_1 < 0$)	$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{X_{1C}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 \geq 1$
Fibre 2 tension ($\sigma_2 > 0$)	$\left(\frac{\sigma_2}{X_{2T}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{23}}{S_{23}}\right)^2 \geq 1$
Fibre 2 compression ($\sigma_2 < 0$)	$\left(\frac{\sigma_2}{X_{2C}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{23}}{S_{23}}\right)^2 \geq 1$
Matrix tension ($\sigma_3 > 0$)	$\left(\frac{\sigma_3}{Y_T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{23}}{S_{23}}\right)^2 \geq 1$
Matrix compression ($\sigma_3 < 0$)	$\left(\frac{\sigma_3}{Y_C}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{23}}{S_{23}}\right)^2 \geq 1$

Table 1: Hashin-Fabric failure criterion [6].

E_{11} (MPa)	E_{22} (MPa)	E_{33} (MPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}	G_{12} (MPa)	G_{13} (MPa)	G_{23} (MPa)	ρ (kg/m ³)
18000	18000	4500	0.25	0.33	0.33	770	2600	2600	1230

Table 2: Elastic properties of Kevlar lamina [7].

X_{1T} (MPa)	X_{1C} (MPa)	X_{2T} (MPa)	X_{2C} (MPa)	X_{3T} (MPa)	X_{3C} (MPa)	S_{12} (MPa)	S_{13} (MPa)	S_{23} (MPa)
555	555	555	555	1050	1050	77	1060	1086

Table 3: Failure properties of Kevlar lamina [7].

2.2 Cellular core

A chopped carbon fibre reinforced nylon (Onyx) is used for the cellular core, with material data taken from experimental tests [8]. The structures investigated in this study had overall dimensions of $130 \times 130 \times 30$ mm. Figure 2 displays the three types of structures analysed: hexagonal (non-auxetic), re-entrant (auxetic), and double arrowhead (auxetic). The base structure consisted of 13 columns and 5 rows (13×5) of the repeating unit cell with a relative density of 30%. The cell size and relative density of these structures were varied during the investigation.

Figure 3: Unit cell representatives of cellular structures under investigation: a) hexagonal (hex), b) re-entrant (RE), c) double arrowhead (DAH).

The relative density is defined as the ratio of the density of the structure to the density of the material that makes up the structure. This is analogous to the volume percent of material in the structure. The wall thickness of the cells was adjusted to change the relative density whilst keeping all other parameters equal. Four relative densities were investigated for each structure: 20%, 30%, 40% and 50%. A geometry with a larger cell size, resulting in a structure with 7 columns and 3 rows (7×3), was also investigated to explore the effect of cell size on the mechanical response of the structure, Figure 4.

Figure 4: Hexagonal, re-entrant and double arrowhead cellular arrays under consideration with small (13×5) and large (7×3) unit cells.

During the impact the maximum displacement of the structure, or the back face deformation (BFD), and the force exerted on the lower clamp were measured. These parameters were used to assess the effect of these parameters on the performance of the structure.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Three 13×5 structures, at 30% relative density, were impacted as described. The peak force and displacement were measured and shown in Table 4.

Structure	Peak force (kN)	Peak displacement (mm)
Hexagonal	21.6	10.0
Re-entrant	14.9	11.9
Double arrowhead	17.0	12.5

Table 4: Peak force and displacement of the structures under impact.

There is a clear reduction in force transmitted to the clamp shown in the case of the auxetic structures, with the re-entrant resulting in the lowest force transferred. There was a smaller variation in the maximum displacement, with the non-auxetic hexagonal structure deforming the least. These results suggest that the auxetic structures are softer than the non-auxetic.

Two cell sizes were investigated, both at 30% relative density. Figure 5 shows that the transmitted force reduced by 20% in the case of the large non-auxetic hexagonal structure. A minor increase in transmitted force was seen for the two auxetic structures. The deformation of both auxetic structures here is folding dominated which explains the relative insensitivity in transmitted force with cell size. The hexagonal structure deforms primarily by bending which could account for the size dependence seen. The overall displacement of the structures was unaffected by the unit cell size, demonstrated in Figure 6.

Figure 5: Peak force for the three structures at two different cell sizes.

Figure 6: Maximum displacement of the three structures at two different cell sizes.

A positive relation was seen between relative density and transmitted force for all unit cells, Figure 7. The discrepancies in transmitted force increased with relative density, with the hexagonal structure having a stronger correlation with density than the auxetics. The higher the density of the structure, the lower the displacement, as illustrated in Figure 8. These results are as expected, in agreement with Gibson & Ashby [9] who predict an increase in modulus with relative density.

Figure 7: Variation of peak transmitted force with relative density for the three structures.

Figure 8: Variation of maximum displacement with relative density for the three structures.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The effect of varying the geometry, size and relative density of a cellular structure, covered by a Kevlar plate, under ballistic impact has been numerically investigated. It was found that the use of auxetic structures, namely re-entrant and double arrowhead, reduced the force transmitted to the clamp significantly compared to a non-auxetic hexagonal structure. This was most prominent at a relative

density of 50% where the double arrowhead structure resulted in a 40% reduction in force compared to the hexagonal. Conversely, the auxetic structures showed an increased displacement under impact compared to the hexagonal structures, with a 2 – 3 mm increase seen between the double arrowhead and the hexagonal. These results illustrate that auxetic structures are softer than non-auxetics.

The size of the unit cell, when overall size and relative density were kept equal, was not shown to affect the maximum displacement for any of the structures investigated. The size of the unit cell did not significantly influence the transmitted force in the case of the auxetics, however a smaller unit cell increased the force considerably for the hexagonal structure. This finding is important for the design of impact-resistant structures as it could influence the choice of unit cell required in situations where size constraints are crucial. The relative density of the structures was shown to have a large influence on the impact response with an increase in transmitted force and a decrease in displacement seen for all structures as relative density was increased.

Overall, it has been shown that the choice of unit cell, as well as the size and relative density can influence the impact behavior. This work provides a basis for the parameter selection when using cellular structures in an impact setting.

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